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Resilience in the City: Exploring the Health Challenges and Policy Recommendations for Climate-induced Migrants in Urban Bangladesh

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive study of the health challenges faced by climate-induced migrants in urban slums of Bangladesh, employing a mixed-methods approach for nuanced insights. Through a survey of 1,476 migrants and subsequent qualitative interviews, focus groups, and observations, the research uncovers stark realities. Quantitatively, the data reveals an alarming rate of health issues among migrants, exacerbated by inadequate healthcare facilities. This is affirmed qualitatively, as migrants articulate their daily struggles, from overcrowded living conditions leading to communicable diseases to mental health deterioration. Gender-specific vulnerabilities also emerge, requiring targeted interventions. Importantly, the study identifies a glaring gap in policy considerations for this marginalized group. Recommendations include immediate enhancements in healthcare infrastructure, gender-sensitive policies, and inclusive urban planning. Policymakers and urban planners will find these findings instrumental in addressing the unique challenges of climate migrants. The research not only adds to the growing body of literature on climate migration but also offers actionable solutions for one of the most pressing humanitarian crises of our times.

Keywords: Climate migration, Healthcare access, Urban slums, Vulnerability, Gender dynamics, Policy gaps

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1 Introduction

The ramifications of climate change on our planet are vast and manifold, with Bangladesh epitomizing the acute vulnerability faced by nations across the globe. As a low-lying deltaic nation, Bangladesh confronts not only the direct environmental repercussions of climate change but also the cascading socio-economic impacts, chiefly migration and urbanization [1, 2]. Recent data from the World Health Organization (WHO) underscore the gravity of the situation, revealing that over 7.1 million Bangladeshis were displaced due to climate change effects in 2022 alone [3]. This figure, alarming in its magnitude, is projected to soar to 13.3 million by 2050. Furthermore, the nation faces the daunting economic burden of these climatic shifts, with climate change siphoning off 1% of its GDP annually. The looming threat of rising sea levels is predicted to submerge approximately 17% of Bangladesh's coastal regions [4], thereby displacing about 20 million residents by 2050. Such figures reinforce Bangladesh's position as the seventh-riskiest nation in the Global Climate Risk Index 2020 [5]. Beyond the native population's displacement, Bangladesh has also provided refuge to over a million forcibly displaced Myanmar nationals since 1978. These individuals, housed in one of the globe's most densely populated camps in Cox's Bazar, bring with them unique medical needs. In an effort to address the multifaceted challenges associated with migration and displacement, the WHO, in collaboration with Bangladesh's Health Ministry, has organized its third annual Global School on Refugee and Migrant Health, an e-learning event with global reach, set to take place in Dhaka. However, the challenges faced by Bangladesh aren't just of an international nature. The country's internal dynamics reveal a complex web of environmental and socio-economic shifts [6]. According to Shafi Mohammad Tareq, a climate expert at Jahangirnagar University, the disruption of fundamental needs such as water, food supply, and work opportunities has driven the internal migration [7]. The increasing salinity and cyclonic activity in Bangladesh's coastal region has impeded agricultural activities and amplified the suffering of local communities. Meanwhile, regions in the west and north grapple with a severe potable water crisis attributed to the unhealthy presence of iron and arsenic in groundwater. The Bangladesh River and Delta Research Centre's findings further highlight the drastic environmental shifts, noting the disappearance of 507 of the country's 1,274 rivers since 1971. Addressing this intricate scenario requires a multifaceted approach. As emphasized during the pre-COP 27 National Consultation on Climate Change and Human Mobility, climate factors are at the forefront of migration and displacement in Bangladesh. The consultation, organized by several notable institutions, seeks to incorporate migration and human mobility dynamics into the broader climate change discussions during the Twenty Seventh Conference of the Parties (COP 27) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). Given the scale of internal displacement, urban centers in Bangladesh are searching for local adaptation solutions. One such initiative is the "People's adaptation plan" piloted in Mongla, the nation's second-largest seaport. With the support of the Global Center on Adaptation (GCA) and BRAC, this plan aims to bolster Mongla's capacities to accommodate climate migrants. The city, already an industrial hub, will offer migrants skills training for formal employment, alternative livelihood opportunities, and a focus on nature-based solutions. Additionally,

with funding from the Asian Development Bank, successful strategies from Mongla are slated to be implemented across various other cities in Bangladesh, offering a blueprint for urban adaptation. As the world grapples with the challenges posed by climate change, nations like Bangladesh stand at the frontline, confronting not only the direct environmental impacts but also the intricate socio-economic consequences. Through a combination of local and international efforts, there's hope that affected communities can find resilience and adapt to the new climate realities. This research aims to address the multifaceted challenges faced by climate migrants in Bangladesh's urban slums, with a particular focus on WASH services and livelihood opportunities in both general and COVID-19 contexts. The objectives of this study are:

1. To assess the challenges/hardships faced by climate migrants in terms of health in Bangladeshi urban slums.
2. To provide a comprehensive representation of the health challenges and needs of climate migrants in urban slum areas.
3. To explore the mental health landscape among these migrants, especially in terms of the prevalence of stress, anxiety, and depression, and to identify existing and potential coping mechanisms.
4. To offer actionable recommendations for policymakers, aiming to enhance the resilience capability of climate migrants regarding health facilities and livelihood prospects.
5. To analyze the gender-specific challenges and opportunities that arise from climate-induced migration, with a special focus on the experiences of women and marginalized groups.
6. To perform a comparative analysis of data from two different slum areas to validate the consistency and reliability of the research findings.
7. To find the role and impact of local governance, NGOs, and community leaders in shaping the experiences of these migrants and addressing their challenges.

Through this research, we hope to shed light on the pressing issues faced by climate migrants in Bangladesh and contribute valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on climate change, migration, and urbanization.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Climate-Induced Migration: A Global Dilemma with Local Impacts

The menace of climate change is no longer a distant threat but a prevailing reality affecting millions globally [8, 9], with the most pronounced impacts being felt in the developing regions of the world. As the planet warms, populations, particularly in the global south, are forced to grapple with unprecedented challenges, one of

which is climate-induced migration. This phenomenon, marked by the large-scale movement of populations triggered by climate-related disasters, is rapidly gaining attention in academic, policy, and international circles.

2.2 Defining Climate Migrants

The discourse surrounding climate migration is complex and multifaceted. The term "climate migrant" itself is subject to debate. Some scholars and policymakers distinguish climate migrants from traditional refugees, advocating for a distinct category and international framework to address their unique needs and challenges [10]. Others, however, caution against overly simplistic or politically charged labels, arguing for a more nuanced understanding of the push and pull factors driving climate-induced human movement [11].

2.3 The Case of Bangladesh

Bangladesh exemplifies a nation at the frontline of climate vulnerability. With a significant portion of its population and land area situated in Low Elevation Coastal Zones, the country faces an existential threat from rising sea levels, intensified cyclones, and other climate adversities [12]. The ND-GAIN Country Index highlights Bangladesh's vulnerability, ranking it as the 20th most susceptible country to climate impacts among 181 nations [13].

2.4 The Human Cost and Response

In 2022, over 7.1 million Bangladeshis were displaced due to climate adversities, a figure projected to soar to 13.3 million by 2050 (WHO). The nation's economic fabric is also strained, with climate change chipping away 1% of its GDP annually. Yet, amidst these challenges, Bangladesh's resilience and adaptive strategies offer insights into managing climate migration.

The government, aware of its resource constraints, views migration as a potential adaptation strategy [14]. Rural-to-urban migration trends, particularly towards cities like Dhaka, are amplified by climate triggers. However, this exacerbates the strain on already overstretched urban centers, spotlighting the essential role of non-profits and international aid in bridging the gap in public service delivery [15].

2.5 International Perspectives and Responses

The international community, including organizations like the UN and WHO, is not oblivious to Bangladesh's plight. Events like the Global School on Refugee and Migrant Health underscore a collective effort to build competence and capacity in addressing migrant health issues amidst climate change. The COP 27 also emerged as a pivotal platform where the intertwining narratives of climate change and human mobility were brought to the fore.

2.6 The Local Landscape

The city of Khulna, a low-lying coastal city, stands as a microcosm of the national narrative, housing a significant population of climate migrants [15]. Here, the impacts of climate change are not just statistical figures but lived realities, with increasing influxes of climate migrants exacerbating resource constraints and highlighting the urgent need for adaptive and resilient urban planning.

2.7 A Glimpse into the Future

As the world navigates the multifaceted challenges of climate change, the narrative of climate migration is poised to become increasingly central. Bangladesh's experience offers not just a glimpse into the human and societal implications of climate change but also insights into adaptive strategies, international collaboration, and policy frameworks that could shape global responses to climate-induced migration in the impending decades.

The literature underscores the urgent and complex nature of climate-induced migration, particularly in vulnerable regions like Bangladesh. There is a consensus on the need for nuanced, multi-faceted, and collaborative approaches to address the challenges and harness the opportunities presented by this emerging dynamic. The intertwining of local experiences and global narratives, policy frameworks, and on-the-ground realities offers a rich tapestry for further research, policy formulation, and international cooperation in the quest for sustainable solutions to climate-induced migration.

3 Methodology

In this chapter, we explore the detailed design and methods that underpin our research. Our objective is to illuminate the experiences of climate migrants in Bangladesh, especially within urban environments, and the challenges they encounter when seeking healthcare. Our research methodology consists of two complementary phases: quantitative and qualitative. The quantitative phase utilizes structured surveys and observations to amass empirical data, setting a numerical backdrop for our study. In contrast, the qualitative phase employs in-depth interviews, focus groups, and direct observations to capture personal narratives and lived experiences. This combination ensures a holistic view, marrying the precision of quantitative data with the depth of qualitative insights. The following sections will further detail the methodologies used to address our central research questions.

3.1 Research Design

In contemporary research, the decision to employ a specific methodological approach is often dictated by the nature of the research question and the desired outcomes. For our study, a mixed-methods approach was deemed most suitable for several compelling reasons:

1. **Comprehensiveness & Depth:** While quantitative methods provide a broad overview, capturing patterns and trends from a larger sample, qual-

itative methods dig deeper, offering insights into individual experiences, perceptions, and narratives. Together, they allow for a comprehensive understanding, merging the "what" with the "why".

2. **Validation & Triangulation:** By employing both quantitative and qualitative methods, we can cross-verify and validate our findings. If similar results or themes emerge from both methods, it enhances the trustworthiness and credibility of the findings. This process, known as triangulation, ensures that our conclusions are not solely based on a singular method's limitations or strengths.
3. **Flexibility in Data Collection:** Climate migration, as a topic, is both vast and intricate. A mixed-methods approach allows for flexibility in data collection. For instance, while surveys might capture general health challenges, interviews can portray personal experiences, uncovering barriers to healthcare access that might not be immediately evident in quantitative data.
4. **Enhanced Interpretability:** The quantitative data can provide a statistical foundation, which when juxtaposed with qualitative narratives, aids in richer interpretation. For instance, while numbers might indicate a significant health challenge among migrants, qualitative data can explain the socio-cultural or economic reasons behind such patterns.
5. **Addressing Complex Research Questions:** Our research questions are multifaceted. Some require statistical analysis to discern patterns, while others necessitate an understanding of personal experiences and perceptions. A mixed-methods approach ensures that our research design is equipped to address this complexity adequately.
6. **Holistic Understanding:** Climate migration and its subsequent challenges encompass socio-cultural, economic, and psychological dimensions. A mixed-methods approach ensures that our research captures this multifaceted phenomenon holistically, without being constrained by the limitations of a singular method.

The mixed-methods approach was not a mere methodological choice but a strategic decision to ensure that our research on climate migration in Bangladesh is both comprehensive and nuanced, capturing the breadth of the phenomenon while not compromising on the depth of individual experiences.

3.2 Phase 1: Quantitative Approach

Survey: Surveys, especially structured questionnaires, are one of the most common methods for collecting quantitative data. These questionnaires are designed with specific, pre-defined questions aiming to gather data systematically from a sample population. The structured nature of these surveys ensures that each participant is presented with the same set of questions in the same order, minimizing variations and biases that could arise from a more open-ended approach. For our research, the administration of these questionnaires was conducted face-to-face (F2F).

The choice of F2F surveys was strategic. Given the sensitive nature of the topic and the potential challenges in reaching out to climate migrants in urban slums, face-to-face interactions ensured a higher response rate and better quality of data. Direct interactions allowed the research team to build a rapport with respondents, clarifying doubts and ensuring that questions were comprehended accurately. This method also provided an opportunity to capture non-verbal cues, which can often be as revealing as verbal responses, especially when discussing personal and potentially distressing experiences.

The structured questionnaire designed for the face-to-face surveys with climate migrants encompassed a range of questions to gather comprehensive insights into their experiences in urban Bangladesh. The survey initiated with the collection of basic demographic details, such as age, gender, region of origin, duration of stay in the current location, and family size. An emphasis was placed on understanding the primary motivations behind their migration, particularly to discern how many moved due to climate-related events. The core section of the survey delved into healthcare access and usage. Participants were queried about any health challenges faced post-migration, their ability to access medical care, and the level of difficulty in doing so. To capture the nuances of their healthcare experiences, they were prompted to identify barriers they encountered, ranging from logistical issues like distance to the healthcare center, to more systemic issues like discrimination. Inclusion of a question about their possession of health insurance or health cards aimed to gauge the formal healthcare support mechanisms available to them. The survey also sought to understand the migrants' perceptions about the difference, if any, in healthcare experiences between migrants and non-migrants. Furthermore, to obtain a broader perspective, participants were asked about their awareness and perceptions of the climate migration discourse within the urban community. To offer participants an avenue to provide more detailed insights, open-ended questions were included, encouraging them to suggest immediate improvements for healthcare access and to mention any community or non-governmental organizations that have been of assistance. Additionally, recognizing the importance of education in shaping experiences and access to resources, the survey incorporated a question about the participants' education level, allowing for an exploration of how educational background may intersect with their healthcare access and overall migration experience.

The dataset contains survey responses from a total of 1,476 participants, collected between January 3, 2023, and September 7, 2023. Of these respondents, 571 are males, representing approximately 38.7% of the sample, while 905 are females, accounting for about 61.3%. The age of the participants spans from a possible anomalous value of -2 years to a maximum of 78 years, with an average age of approximately 39.87 years. It's important to note that there appears to be some inconsistencies in the age data, suggesting further scrutiny or data cleaning might be necessary.

Structured Observations:

Structured observations are a data collection method where researchers observe specific behaviors or conditions and quantify them using a predetermined scale or checklist. Unlike casual or unstructured observations, where observations might

be random or unspecific, this method is systematic and focuses on pre-decided parameters.

For our study, structured observations were intended to complement the data derived from surveys. While surveys provided insights into the perceptions and self-reported experiences of migrants, structured observations allowed the researchers to objectively assess the living conditions, interactions, daily activities, and other relevant dynamics in the migrants' environment. The use of a checklist ensured that observations were consistent across different locations and times, allowing for comparisons and analyses. This method was particularly crucial in understanding the tangible challenges faced by migrants, such as housing conditions, access to amenities, and visible health and hygiene practices.

Sampling Methods:

In order to capture a comprehensive and relevant set of experiences from climate migrants, a combination of purposive and snowball sampling methods was employed. Initially, participants were selected purposefully, ensuring they had migrated due to climate adversities within the past five years. This ensured their experiences were both recent and directly tied to the phenomena under study. Recognizing the inherent challenges in accessing this specific population and fostering an environment of trust, snowball sampling was then utilized. Initial participants were asked to refer other potential migrants they knew, leading to a richer and more diverse set of participants. This method not only facilitated access but also often led to more candid and in-depth discussions, as referrals came with a pre-established degree of trust.

- **Purposive Sampling:** Purposive sampling involves intentionally selecting specific individuals or groups who possess certain characteristics or knowledge deemed important for the study.
- **Snowball Sampling:** Snowball sampling is especially useful when studying hard-to-reach populations. After interviewing an initial participant, the researcher asks for referrals to other potential participants.

Data Analysis

To garner meaningful insights from the collected data and ensure its comprehensive interpretation, a multi-pronged approach to data analysis will be adopted. The objective is to not only understand the data at face value but to also discern patterns, relationships, and potential underlying causes for observed trends.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics will serve as the foundational layer of our analysis. This involves summarizing the main aspects of the data to present a clear picture of the survey results. Key metrics will include:

- **Central Tendency Measures:** The mean (average), median (middle value), and mode (most frequent value) will be calculated for each question, providing a general sense of the responses.
- **Spread Measures:** The standard deviation and variance will be calculated to understand the variability or dispersion of the responses. This informs us

about the spread of the data around the mean and indicates the consistency of the responses.

- **Frequency Distributions:** Histograms and bar charts will be used to visually represent the distribution of responses for each question.

Validity and Reliability

Ensuring the trustworthiness and robustness of our research findings is of paramount importance. Validity pertains to the accuracy of our tools and methods, ensuring that we are genuinely measuring what we intend to measure. For our survey, this means that the questions were designed to accurately capture the experiences, perceptions, and challenges of climate migrants concerning healthcare access. On the other hand, reliability addresses the consistency of our tools. In the context of our study, it signifies that if the survey were to be administered multiple times under similar conditions, it would yield consistent results. To enhance both validity and reliability, our survey underwent a rigorous design process, which included a review of existing literature, expert consultations, and pilot testing to refine and optimize the questions for our target population.

Ethical Considerations

Conducting research, especially within vulnerable communities such as climate migrants, requires a deep commitment to ethical principles to ensure the dignity, rights, safety, and well-being of participants. Foremost, informed consent was sought from all participants, ensuring they understood the purpose of the research, its procedures, potential benefits, and risks. Participants were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without any repercussions. Confidentiality was paramount. All data collected was anonymized, ensuring that personal identifiers were removed or encrypted, protecting the identity of participants. Any sensitive or potentially distressing questions were approached with caution, ensuring participants felt comfortable and supported. Additionally, safe and secure storage measures were put in place for the data, ensuring that only authorized personnel had access. The research was also conducted transparently, with respect for the values and culture of the communities involved, and all findings are to be shared with the participants, ensuring they are kept in the loop and can benefit from the outcomes of the study.

Practical Considerations

Before the full deployment of the survey, a pilot test was conducted to refine questions and ensure their clarity, while also testing the practical logistics of data collection. To guarantee consistency and accuracy during the data collection phase, all survey administrators underwent comprehensive training on the survey's objectives, ethical considerations, and best practices. To enhance the response rate, strategies such as follow-up reminders and clear communication of the survey's importance to participants were employed. The survey itself was designed with a focus on clarity, using concise questions and Likert scales to capture nuanced responses, ensuring the ease of comprehension and completion for respondents.

3.3 Phase II: Qualitative Approach

The qualitative phase of our research focuses into the human experiences and narratives, capturing the richness of individual stories and offering a nuanced understanding of the challenges and perspectives of climate migrants in urban Bangladesh.

Data Collection Methods

- **In-depth Interviews:** These are structured yet open-ended conversations that allow participants to share their personal experiences, perspectives, and insights. The primary purpose of these interviews is to understand the lived experiences of climate migrants, their struggles, coping mechanisms, and aspirations. By enabling a dialogue, we aim to capture the depth and breadth of their experiences, going beyond mere numbers.
- **Focus Groups:** These are structured discussions involving a small group of participants. The rationale behind focus groups is to foster a collaborative environment where participants can discuss, debate, and share their experiences. It aids in identifying common themes, shared experiences, and even divergent views, providing a holistic view of the community's perspectives.
- **Observations:** Observational checklists were employed to systematically gather data on housing conditions, social interactions, economic activities, daily life, and more in the slums. This method offers a firsthand view of the migrants' living conditions, providing tangible evidence to support or challenge the narratives collected through interviews and focus groups.

The qualitative phase of the research encompassed in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and observational methodologies to delve deeper into the lived experiences of climate migrants in Bangladeshi urban slums. Data collection spanned from January 15, 2023, to September 15, 2023.

In-depth Interviews:

A total of 45 interviews were conducted, spanning a duration of 30 to 90 minutes each. Participants comprised 30 climate migrants residing in Dhaka's slums and 15 healthcare providers offering services in the region. The interviews revolved around personal experiences, healthcare access challenges, and perceived gaps in service delivery.

Focus Group Discussions:

Six focus group discussions were held, each consisting of 6-8 participants. These discussions were aimed at understanding common themes, shared challenges, and potential community-driven solutions. Participants engaged in lively debates, highlighting the collective struggles and hopes of the migrant community.

Observations:

Field visits to the slums, lasting approximately 60-90 minutes each, offered a firsthand view of the migrants' living conditions, interactions, economic activities, and daily life. Observational checklists were used to record details about housing types,

basic amenities, safety and security measures, and social interactions among other facets. Field visits to the slums, lasting approximately 60-90 minutes each, offered a firsthand view of the migrants' living conditions, interactions, economic activities, and daily life. Observational checklists were used to record details about housing types, basic amenities, safety and security measures, and social interactions among other facets.

Key Themes Identified:

- **Healthcare Access Barriers:** Financial constraints, lack of awareness, and distant healthcare facilities were frequently cited as impediments.
- **Mental Health Concerns:** Many migrants voiced feelings of isolation, stress, and anxiety, magnified by the urban environment's challenges.
- **Gender Disparities:** Female migrants often faced additional challenges, especially concerning safety, healthcare accessibility, and employment opportunities.
- **Community Cohesion:** Despite the challenges, a strong sense of community and mutual support was evident among the migrants.

The qualitative findings provided rich, contextual data, complementing the quantitative results and offering a more holistic understanding of the challenges and aspirations of the climate migrants.

Data Analysis

Thematic Analysis: After transcribing the interviews and focus group discussions, a thematic analysis was conducted. This involves identifying, analyzing, and interpreting patterns or "themes" within the qualitative data. It's a way to see the bigger picture by understanding how different pieces of data fit into a cohesive narrative.

Narrative Analysis: This method focuses on the stories that participants tell, helping us understand their personal journeys, struggles, and successes. By analyzing these narratives, we get a clearer picture of the individual paths that make up the collective experience of the community.

Trustworthiness

- **Triangulation:** To ensure the validity of our findings, we used multiple data sources and methods. By comparing and cross-referencing data from interviews, focus groups, and observations, we aimed to provide a well-rounded understanding of the issues.
- **Member Checking:** Participants were given the opportunity to review and validate the findings, ensuring that our interpretations align with their intended messages and experiences.
- **Rich, Thick Descriptions:** Detailed accounts of participants' experiences were provided, allowing readers to fully grasp the context and determine the applicability of our findings to other scenarios or populations.

4 Results

The repercussions of climate change manifest in numerous ways, with human migration being one of its most profound consequences. Bangladesh, being at the forefront of climate vulnerability, witnesses a significant influx of climate migrants into its urban centers. This study aims to unravel the complexities of their experiences, with an emphasis on healthcare access.

4.1 Quantitative analysis

Amidst the unfolding narrative of climate change, Bangladesh stands as a poignant testament to the human repercussions of environmental disruptions. Urban centers, often seen as sanctuaries of opportunity, draw in a multitude of migrants. Yet, these urban promises often stand in stark contrast to the realities faced by climate migrants, especially in the domain of healthcare access.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Participant Characteristics

Variable	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation	Mode	Variance
Age	39.87	40.0	11.39	42	129.79
Duration of stay in the current location (Year)	2.9	3.0	2.45	3	5.98
Number of family members	5.38	5.0	1.69	5	2.87

Demographics and Migration Causes

The data reveals a gender disparity among the respondents with 38.7% being male and a larger 61.3% being female. This could hint at gender-specific migration trends or differences in survey participation. Educationally, a significant portion of these migrants possess only primary education, potentially influencing their urban opportunities and health awareness. Environmental adversities prominently emerge as migration triggers. A staggering 57% of respondents identified "Natural Disasters" as their primary reason for migration, closely followed by 43% pointing to "Sea Level Rise". Other environmental factors, like "Riverbank Erosion" (37%) and "Loss of Agricultural Productivity" (35%), further emphasize the environmental drivers behind these migration trends.

Health Concerns Among Migrants

Health emerges as a pressing concern for this community. A notable 82% of respondents reported facing health issues post-migration, highlighting the strains of the migration journey and potential inadequacies in urban health facilities. Further, when comparing healthcare experiences, 65% felt that migrants faced inferior healthcare access compared to non-migrants, suggesting systemic disparities.

Awareness and Perception Challenges

A significant 73% of respondents felt that urban populations lacked a comprehensive understanding of climate migration challenges. This underscores a potential knowledge gap that might be contributing to policy lacunae and social misunderstandings.

The exploratory analysis paints a picture of a community grappling with the aftereffects of environmental challenges, seeking better opportunities and health-care in urban areas, yet facing a new set of challenges upon arrival. The insights underscore the urgent need for more comprehensive policies and programs to address the health needs of climate migrants. Additionally, there's a call for increased awareness campaigns and educational programs to bridge the understanding gap in urban communities about the realities of climate-induced migration. The journey of climate migrants, as illuminated by this analysis, is fraught with challenges. Yet, with the right interventions, policy adjustments, and awareness efforts, a more inclusive and understanding urban environment can be fostered for them.

4.2 Qualitative Analysis

In-depth Interviews:

Theme 1 - Health Concerns:

Migrants frequently expressed severe health challenges, with one respondent poignantly stating, "Since we moved here, my child has been sick thrice. The nearest clinic is miles away, and we cannot afford private care." The overcrowded conditions in their living quarters often lead to communicable diseases. Mental health issues also emerge as significant concerns, with one respondent revealing, "Every night is uncertain. We worry about our children's future in this city." The overcrowded conditions in their living quarters are a fertile ground for communicable diseases. As one local healthcare provider put it, "Diseases spread fast here. One person gets a fever, and soon, half the settlement is down with it." These observations shed light on the precarious nature of public health in densely populated migrant areas and the potential risks of disease outbreaks. Mental health issues, while less overt, were a recurrent theme. The psychological toll of displacement, coupled with the daily urban struggles, weighs heavily on the migrants. One respondent revealed, "Every night is uncertain. We worry about our children's future in this city." Another shared, "The noise, the pollution, the constant fear of eviction - it's a daily battle for sanity." Several women also voiced concerns about reproductive and maternal health. "There's no place here for prenatal check-ups, and hospital births are too expensive," lamented a young expectant mother. The lack of gender-sensitive healthcare services further exacerbates the vulnerabilities of female migrants. In a telling narrative, an elderly migrant shared, "Back in the village, we had clean air and space. Here, the air feels heavy, and there's no space even to breathe." The transition from rural to urban settings, while driven by necessity, poses significant environmental health challenges, from polluted air to contaminated water sources.

Theme 2 - Livelihood Struggles:

A recurring narrative centered around job insecurity and exploitative labor conditions. "I work 14 hours a day, and still, it's hand-to-mouth. There's no job security," shared one migrant, reflecting the vulnerabilities of working in the informal sector.

Theme 3 - Adaptation:

Despite numerous challenges, stories of resilience emerged. "We create our little support groups, share resources, and look out for each other," commented a young

mother, emphasizing the strength of informal networks within the migrant community.

Focus Groups:

Theme 1 - Community Cohesion:

The shared experience of migration has fostered community ties. However, these bonds sometimes strain due to resource competition. One group participant mentioned, "Water is scarce. Sometimes, neighbors end up quarreling over access to the community tap."

Theme 2 - Gender Dynamics:

: A recurring theme from women's narratives is the heightened sense of vulnerability they experience in their new urban settings. This vulnerability is multifaceted, spanning from concerns about personal safety to gender-specific health needs. One respondent shared, "The lanes are narrow and often dark. I avoid going out after sunset. It's just not safe." Such sentiments hint at the challenges women face in accessing basic amenities or even earning a livelihood due to security concerns. Yet, in the face of these vulnerabilities, women's narratives also radiate resilience and agency. "There are days I fear for my safety, but I also lead a group of women in the community to share resources and support each other," shared a female respondent. These informal women-led networks become vital lifelines, ensuring collective access to resources, information, and emotional support. Another dimension that emerged was the economic role many women have assumed. "Back in our village, I would only do household chores. Here, I make handicrafts and sell them in the local market. It's tough, but it helps feed my children," expressed another respondent. Such narratives underscore the economic adaptations women make, often stepping into roles they wouldn't traditionally occupy, demonstrating their adaptability and strength. Sexual and reproductive health emerged as a significant concern among female respondents. "There's no place to go for check-ups, and there's little privacy. Discussing these things is taboo here," lamented a young woman, highlighting the socio-cultural barriers that compound the lack of healthcare infrastructure. However, on the flip side, women also highlighted instances where they used their gender roles to their advantage. "People in the city often trust women more. I have been able to negotiate better deals for my goods because they see me as less threatening," shared a female trader.

Theme 3 - Policy Gaps:

: One of the most striking revelations from the interviews and focus groups was the perceived disconnect between the migrants' lived realities and the policies meant to serve them. The notion of being left behind, not just in physical amenities but also in the larger narrative of urban development, was palpable.

A sentiment echoed across multiple narratives was the feeling of being 'invisible' to policy-makers. "The city talks about big projects, building skyscrapers and shopping malls, but who thinks about us? We are also part of this city. We need basic facilities," voiced a respondent. Such expressions are indicative of a pervasive feeling of policy neglect.

Another respondent shared, "When there's flooding, the news shows areas where the elite live. Our homes get submerged too, but no one comes to see." This highlights not just the lack of responsive policies but also a sense of media neglect,

furthering their feeling of invisibility.

It wasn't just about neglect; it was also about the inadequacy of existing policies. Some respondents were aware of policies meant for their welfare but found them impractical. "There are policies, but they're on paper. We don't know how to access them, and when we try, there are so many hurdles," shared another migrant, pointing towards the implementation gaps.

The women, especially, highlighted the absence of gender-sensitive policies. "There are health camps sometimes, but they don't address our specific needs as women. Where do we go for maternal care? For our safety concerns?" questioned a female respondent, hinting at the lack of comprehensive, gender-inclusive policy planning.

Furthermore, the youth among the migrants expressed concerns about educational opportunities. "We moved to the city hoping for a better future for our children. But where are the schools for them? How will they rise out of this life if there are no policies to educate them?" This sentiment underscores the inter-generational implications of policy gaps.

Observations: Housing and Living Conditions:

Visible signs of makeshift homes, overcrowded spaces, and inadequate WASH facilities were prevalent. Observers noted the palpable vulnerability of the environment to diseases and natural adversities

Economic Activities:

Most migrants were engaged in daily wage jobs, often in unhygienic conditions. Observations also highlighted children and women working, suggesting economic pressures on families.

Social Interactions:

While internal community bonds appeared strong, there was a discernible boundary separating migrants from the broader urban populace, hinting at social exclusions.

Insights & Interpretations: The qualitative findings, enriched by direct narratives, corroborate, and deepen the quantitative insights. The voices of migrants underscore an urgent need for targeted interventions, policy attention, and community-level initiatives. The narratives weave a tale of challenges but also of resilience, hope, and community strength

5 Conclusion

The multifaceted challenges faced by climate migrants in urban Bangladeshi slums have been brought to the forefront in this study. The quantitative findings shed light on the pressing health concerns and perceived gaps in healthcare access. This was further deepened by the qualitative analysis, where the lived experiences of migrants painted a vivid picture of their daily struggles, resilience, and aspirations. Particularly telling were the narratives that underscored the urgency of health issues and the nuanced challenges women face. Furthermore, the overwhelming sentiment of being overlooked in policy considerations resonates with a broader global challenge of recognizing and addressing the needs of climate migrants. The data underscores the need for a holistic approach, considering both immediate healthcare interventions and long-term policy solutions. While this study provides valuable insights

into the challenges and perspectives of climate migrants in urban Bangladeshi slums, it is not without its limitations. Firstly, the sample size, though substantial, may not capture the entirety of diversity and depth of experiences of all migrants. The urban slums are heterogeneous, and experiences may differ based on various factors not extensively covered in this research, such as specific regional backgrounds, time since migration, or nuances in socio-economic status. Secondly, the qualitative approach, although enriching, relies on self-reported data, which might be influenced by recall bias or participants' hesitancy to share sensitive information. Looking forward, there is a vast scope for more granular research that dives deeper into specific challenges, such as mental health concerns or gender-specific vulnerabilities. Longitudinal studies that track the journey of migrants over time can offer insights into the evolving challenges and their adaptive strategies. Additionally, expanding the geographical scope to include other urban centers in Bangladesh or comparing the experiences of migrants in different countries can further enrich our understanding of this global phenomenon. Given the pronounced health concerns among the migrants, there is an urgent need to bolster healthcare infrastructure in urban slums. This includes not just physical healthcare facilities, but also outreach programs, health awareness campaigns, and mental health support mechanisms tailored specifically for the unique challenges faced by migrants. The study underscored the distinct challenges faced by female migrants. It's imperative for policies to be gender-responsive, offering protection against gender-based vulnerabilities, and at the same time, leveraging the strengths of women as community leaders and caregivers. As urban centers continue to attract climate migrants, city planning needs to be more inclusive. This includes ensuring affordable housing, access to basic amenities, and creating opportunities for economic integration of migrants. There's a clear gap in understanding the challenges of climate migration among the broader urban populace. Awareness campaigns, educational programs, and advocacy initiatives can play a pivotal role in bridging this gap, fostering more inclusive urban communities. Policymakers should recognize the 'invisible' plight of these migrants and draft integrative policies that address not just their immediate needs but also pave the way for their long-term well-being and integration into urban life. Leveraging the strong community bonds among migrants can be pivotal. Encouraging and supporting community-led initiatives, self-help groups, and resource-sharing networks can go a long way in ensuring the sustainable well-being of these migrants.

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